

Determination of the Composition, Stability Constants and Activation Parameters of UO_2^{2+} -Hexamethylenetetramine Complexes at Dropping Mercury Electrode*

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Manuscript received 12 September 1979, accepted 31 December 1979

Polarographic reduction of complexation reactions of hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA) with uranyl ion in 1.0M KOAc at dme studied were found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled involving one electron transfer, the slope of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs E plot being 60 ± 2 mV. The effect of pH on the complex formation was studied and pH 4.5 was selected for the study of the present system. Stability constants of the complexes were determined by DeFord and Hume method at different temperatures (25, 30 and 35°) and the activation parameters were also calculated. The mono-dentate HMTA forms tetra co-ordinated complex with UO_2^{2+} ion and the stability constants for different species existing in solution UO_2L^{2+} , $\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2^{2+}$, $\text{UO}_2\text{L}_3^{2+}$ and $\text{UO}_2\text{L}_4^{2+}$ were calculated. The negative of the stability constants for $\text{UO}_2\text{L}_3^{2+}$ indicates that this species is not existing or highly unstable in solution. The plot of percentage distribution of metal ion present in the form of various species at 25° have also been reported.

RESULTS of an investigation of the electrolytic reduction of the complexes formed by hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA) with some of the metal ions at a mercury dropping electrode in different electrolytes and also at different temperatures were published earlier¹⁻³. Though there are many publications dealt with the electrochemical reduction of uranyl ion with some of the amines⁴⁻⁸, but however the present work describes the detailed study of the complexation reactions of uranyl ion with HMTA as complexing agent and again then stereochemistry of uranyl ion as UO_2 -HMTA complexes are going to be similar to some of the metal ions studied earlier with HMTA, say Ni and Cu^{2+} . Although the reduction of uranyl-amine complexes were found to be a single electron transfer process as was in the case of majority of the earlier literature work⁴⁻⁸, most of the reports are only the overall stability constants. For the reduction of UO_2 -HMTA complexes in 1.0M KOAc as supporting electrolyte, reversible one electron transfer prevails over the potential range studied and stability constants and composition of different species formed are investigated at different temperatures.

Experimental

Materials: Uranyl acetate (BDH, AR), Hexamethylenetetramine (Reidel, Germany) were used without further purification. Potassium acetate and triton-X-100 (BDH) lab reagents are used as

supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. Triply distilled mercury was used as mercury pool.

Instrumentation and methods: The polarographic measurements were made using a manual Toshniwal polarograph type CLO 2A in conjunction with the multiflex galvanometer. The electrolytic cell and the procedure adopted are the same as was described in the earlier papers¹⁻³. The half-wave potentials reported here were with respect to the saturated calomel electrode. Before the electrolysis, the experimental solutions prepared with the conductivity water were degassed with purified nitrogen.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the half-wave potentials of UO_2 -HMTA system in 1.0M KOAc was studied over a pH range of 3.5 to 6.5 and $E_{1/2}$ vs pH graph was plotted (Fig. 1). To avoid the hydrolysed product at high pH and also to have the half-wave potential shifts to moderately negative values, pH 4.5 was selected for the study of the present system.

The polarographic reduction of 1mM UO_2^{2+} ion concentration over the concentration range of HMTA in 1.0M KOAc as supporting electrolyte and 0.002% triton-X-100 maxima suppressor, gave

* A part of this work was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1978 held at Waltair,
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Fig. 1. Plot of pH vs $E_{1/2}$ for UO_2^{2+} -HMTA system at 25°C in 1.0M Potassium acetate.

well defined single waves. The reduction of the complexes in each case was a reversible diffusion controlled process and the slopes of the log plots are being 60 ± 2 mV.

Data analysis ;

Since the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_x$ is not a linear plot or a smooth curve, but appears to be as many as four segments, therefore the system involves mixture of consecutively formed complex ions but not single final complex species. Hence DeFord and Hume method^{9,10} of calculations were applied for evaluation of formation constants of different UO_2 -HMTA complexes. The $E_{1/2}$ values as a function of concentration of the ligand were used to calculate $F_0(X)$ function from the equation

$$F_0(X) = \text{Antilog} [0.4343(nF/RT)\Delta(E_{1/2}) + \log I_s/I_0]$$

where $F_0(X)$ represents the experimentally measured quantity on the right hand side of the equation. In order to determine K_1 to K_n , the graphical extrapolation method devised by Leden¹¹ was applied. The intercepts of these extrapolated plots correspond to the formation constants values for K_1 to K_n respectively. For verification, the limiting slopes of $F_n(X)$ vs $[X]$ were taken and these values were found to be equal to corresponding K_n . The possible complexes therefore are UO_2L^{2+} , $UO_2L_2^{2+}$, $UO_2L_3^{2+}$ and $UO_2L_4^{2+}$ where L is HMTA and the possible reactions at dme are

In solution

At dme

These reduction reactions were carried out at three different temperatures under the identical conditions. From the formation constants data, it is seen that very weak complexes were formed. The trend in increase in the i_d and decrease in formation constant values with increase in temperature were as per the phenomena⁸.

Activation Parameters :

The activation parameters have been calculated from the formation constants data at three different temperatures 25, 30 and 35°, substituting in the respective equations

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K_{stab}$$

$$\log = K_2/K_1 = [\Delta H(T_2 - T_1)]/4.576T_2T_1$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S = [\Delta H - \Delta G]/\Delta T$$

and these values are summarised in Table 2. The distribution of uranyl ion present in various forms as a function of the ligand concentration was calculated and plotted as percentage distribution vs $\log C_x$ (Fig. 2). The experimental data is tabulated

Fig. 2. Percentage Distribution of metal ion as different species vs logarithmic concentration of HMTA at 25° in 1.0M Potassium acetate.

TABLE 1a—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA AND ANALYSIS OF $F_n(X)$ VALUES FOR THE UO_2^{2+} -HMTA SYSTEM IN KOAC MEDIUM AT 25, 30 AND 35°C (pH 4.5)

HMTA M	i_d (μA)	25°C		i_d (μA)	30°C		i_d (μA)	35°C	
		$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$F_0(X)$		$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$F_0(X)$		$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$F_0(X)$
0.00	10.760	0.475	1.00	12.300	0.476	1.00	14.640	0.482	1.00
0.20	9.374	0.488	1.91	11.500	0.478	1.88	12.160	0.496	2.04
0.40	9.305	0.492	2.25	10.470	0.492	2.10	12.890	0.499	2.16
0.80	7.615	0.510	5.53	8.642	0.510	5.24	10.540	0.514	4.64
1.00	6.372	0.515	7.07	7.762	0.515	7.86	8.933	0.523	7.70
1.20	5.705	0.524	12.12	7.615	0.524	10.18	8.790	0.532	11.00
1.60	5.056	0.537	24.00	6.298	0.540	12.74	6.884	0.542	20.46
1.80	4.834	0.565	74.46	5.056	0.558	56.53	6.446	0.568	58.29
2.00	3.552	0.566	67.61	3.955	0.573	128.30	4.834	0.560	57.48
2.20	3.076	0.566	121.60	3.662	0.574	144.10	5.126	0.569	76.08
2.40	3.076	0.578	194.30	2.783	0.578	169.00	4.909	0.582	129.80

TABLE 1b—SUMMARISED STABILITY CONSTANTS DATA OF DIFFERENT SPECIES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Complex species	Stability constants at		
	25°C	30°C	35°C
UO_2L^{2+}	2.50	2.00	1.75
$UO_2L_2^{2+}$	3.80	3.30	2.50
$UO_2L_3^{2+}$	-1.14	-1.30	-0.58
$UO_2L_4^{2+}$	1.25	1.13	1.01

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR UO_2^{2+} -HMTA SYSTEM

Temperature °C	$\Delta G(Kcal)$	$\Delta H(Kcal)$	$\Delta S(cal/Deg./Mole)$
25	-0.013	-	-
30	-0.007	-3.622	-12.02
35	-0.0006	-4.164	-13.62

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in Table 1. The negative values of the stability constants of $UO_2L_3^{2+}$ at different temperatures indicates that this species is not existing or highly unstable in solution. The variation in the stability constant values at different temperatures apart from the above mentioned factors might be accounted from the entropy change, steric and electrostatic effects in addition to the statistical considerations.